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Journal of Business and Economic Analysis, Vol. 7, No. 2 (2025) 106-133

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.20839747

Enhancing Entrepreneurship Education Outcomes through Curriculum Fidelity: Do Regulatory Frameworks Make a Difference?

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Received 15 November 2025

Revised 6 May 2026

Accepted 11 May 2026

Published 15 June 2026

Abstract

Aligning with Sustainable Development Goal 8, which emphasises decent work and economic growth, entrepreneurship education (EE) has been recognised as a tactical instrument for fostering innovation and economic resilience. Despite its potential, uneven outcomes in higher education institutions (HEIs) have limited the effectiveness of EE integration into curricula. This study investigates the impact of curriculum fidelity, the extent to which entrepreneurship curricula are delivered as designed, on entrepreneurship education outcomes (EEOs), including entrepreneurial mindset, intention, and action, and examines the moderating role of regulatory frameworks in this relationship. Cross-sectional data were collected from lecturers delivering entrepreneurship courses across universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education in South-West Nigeria. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) was employed to test the proposed conceptual model. The results indicate that curriculum fidelity exerts a significant positive effect on EEOs, confirming that consistent and faithful implementation enhances students' entrepreneurial capabilities. In contrast, the regulatory framework exerts a significant negative moderating effect on the fidelity–EEOs link, suggesting that rigid or overly prescriptive policy may lessen the benefits of high-fidelity curriculum delivery. These findings amplify the EE discourse by highlighting the dual importance of implementation fidelity and the regulatory environment, demonstrating that while fidelity is critical for effective outcomes, policy design can either constrain or facilitate its impact. By integrating curriculum fidelity and regulatory considerations, the study provides practical implications for curriculum designers, policymakers, and higher institutions managers, emphasising the necessity of regulatory flexibility that preserves

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pedagogical integrity while enabling adaptive curriculum delivery to optimise policy ambition into measurable improvements in entrepreneurial mindset, intention, and action.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurship education outcomes, Curriculum implementation fidelity, Education policy frameworks*

Paper type: Research paper

1. Introduction

Entrepreneurship education (EE) is a multidimensional effort that blends curricular and co-curricular pedagogies to cultivate opportunity recognition, value creation, adaptability, and venture competencies through experiential and reflective learning. It influences proximal outcomes, mindset, self-efficacy and skills, and, in favourable conditions, results in entrepreneurial action (Nabi et al., 2017; Wong & Chan, 2022). Beyond individual gains, EE drives institutional and policy strategies to stimulate innovation, employability, and ecosystem vibrancy by linking graduate capacities to knowledge spillovers (Lehmann et al., 2020; Rocha et al., 2024).

Echoing the European Commission's definition, UNESCO frames EE as a lifelong competence supporting both personal growth and social inclusion (Rodrigues, 2025). The field recognises multiple approaches, *for, in, about, and through* entrepreneurship, each emphasising different learning logics and contexts (Ndofirepi, 2020). Consequently, EE is increasingly positioned as a lever for the Sustainable Development Goals, particularly SDG 4 (quality education), SDG 5 (gender equality), and SDG 8 (decent work and growth) (Zaring et al., 2019; Al-Lawati et al., 2022; Talukder et al., 2024), while also nurturing entrepreneurial culture and lifelong learning for personal, social, and national development (Iwu, 2022; Igbokwe et al., 2023). Theoretically, this promise rests on human capital theory and institutional theory, grounding EE in complementary micro-capability and macro-context perspectives (Becker, 1964; Burns, 2017; Maritz et al., 2020; Lamine et al., 2021).

Despite widespread adoption, entrepreneurship education outcomes (EEOs) or entrepreneurial outcomes remain uneven because regulatory environments and curriculum fidelity vary markedly across systems. For example, while national agencies like, National Universities Commission (NUC), National Board for Technical Education (NBTE), and National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE), standardise curricula, accreditation, and quality benchmarks to assure consistency (Bello & Onyeocha, 2023; Ilawagbon, 2025) in Nigeria, the United

Kingdom's emphasis on institutional autonomy fosters innovation but can compromise fidelity and produce variable outcomes, a pattern mirrored across Europe (Boer & Enders, 2017). Cross-level evidence indicates that accreditation, qualification frameworks, and policy incentives condition EE's effects on entrepreneurial intention (EI) and entrepreneurial action (EA) (Walter & Block, 2016; Makhoul, 2019; Huang et al., 2021; Ripollés & Blesa, 2023).

In Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), misalignments among curriculum, pedagogy, and monitoring aggravate variability. The Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) embeds entrepreneurship at the senior secondary level by mandating one compulsory entrepreneurship subject among thirty-five trade options (Ajose, 2021). In contrast, EE is mostly restricted to tertiary institutions in Lesotho (Thetsane, 2023). Pedagogically, Nigerian polytechnics combine theory with practice, while some Kenyan polytechnics rely on lecture-based formats (Adeyemo et al., 2021; John et al., 2022), and persistent deficits in evaluation methods, infrastructure, and mentorship limit transformation across SSA (Ahmed & Ahmed, 2021; Omotosho et al., 2024). Institutional theory insights help explain these patterns: incentives, rules, and quality assurance practices shape curriculum fidelity and entrepreneurial outcomes (Walter & Block, 2016; Urbano et al., 2019).

Although EE programmes and accreditation frameworks are widely adopted in Nigeria, outcomes remain uneven, often shaped by lecturer workload, institutional capacity, and discretion in delivering experiential components (Yatu et al., 2018; Oyinlola et al., 2024; Harvey, 2024; Ofosu-Appiah et al., 2025). At the centre of this variability is curriculum fidelity, the extent to which programmes are delivered as designed with appropriate pedagogy and assessment. When fidelity is weak, implementation becomes inconsistent, producing fragmented and unpredictable outcomes that fall short of policy expectations (Stains & Vickrey, 2017; de Leeuw et al., 2020).

Despite a growing body of research on EE, a key gap persists in understanding how implementation processes interact with institutional conditions to shape outcomes (EEOs). Existing studies largely examine the direct effects of EE on entrepreneurial mindset, intention, and action, often assuming uniform delivery and overlooking variations in curriculum fidelity (Nabi et al., 2017; Wong & Chan, 2022). Similarly, research on regulatory frameworks tends to emphasise their direct role in ensuring quality and performance in higher education, with limited attention to how such frameworks condition the effectiveness of curriculum implementation (Walter & Block, 2016; Urbano et al., 2019; Lamine et al., 2021). This disconnect is particularly evident in Sub-

Saharan Africa, where policy standardisation coexists with uneven delivery practices, infrastructural limitations, and pedagogical inconsistencies that shape outcomes (Iwu, 2022; Omotosho et al., 2024). As a result, the interaction between curriculum fidelity and regulatory frameworks remains under-examined, leaving limited empirical insight into how these forces jointly shape EE outcomes in the region.

Therefore, this study addresses the persistent gap between policy aspiration and expected outcomes by investigating curriculum fidelity and regulatory frameworks as joint mechanisms that shape EE's effectiveness. Specifically, it will: (i) examine how curriculum fidelity influences entrepreneurship education outcomes, including entrepreneurial mindset, intention, and action, (ii) evaluate whether regulatory frameworks shape the effectiveness of EE delivery, (iii) assess the impact of the regulatory framework on EEOs, and (iv) analyse the moderating role of regulatory frameworks on the relationship between curriculum fidelity and EEOs.

Theoretically, this research contributes by bridging human capital theory and institutional theory to explain how capability development (through high-fidelity implementation) interacts with regulatory structures to produce entrepreneurial outcomes. It introduces curriculum fidelity as a multidimensional construct within EE research and positions regulation not merely as a direct determinant, but as a boundary condition that can amplify or constrain implementation effectiveness. Empirically, the study provides novel evidence from South-West Nigerian higher education institutions using PLS-SEM, offering one of the few quantitative examinations of the fidelity–regulation interaction in EE within Sub-Saharan Africa. Practically, the findings inform policymakers and educators on how to design regulatory frameworks that ensure quality without undermining pedagogical flexibility.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical insight

Human capital theory (HCT) positions EE as a deliberate investment in developing students' entrepreneurial knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSAs). These capabilities form the foundation for opportunity recognition, intention formation, and action. Empirical studies (Nabi et al., 2017; Wong & Chan, 2022) consistently characterise EE as a mechanism for capability-building, demonstrating that experiential and feedback-rich programmes are particularly effective in enhancing entrepreneurial mindset, intention, and action. Therefore, entrepreneurial outcomes are

contingent on the quality and depth of skill acquisition, framing education as both a predictive and facilitative lever for entrepreneurial behaviour.

Conversely, institutional theory highlights the role of norms, formal structures, and regulatory mechanisms in shaping outcomes. Quality-assurance (QA) protocols, accreditation standards, and national policies establish expectations for curriculum design, among others, which can either constrain or support the translation of EE into tangible entrepreneurial outcomes. Comparative evidence (Walter & Block, 2016; Ripollés & Blesa, 2023) suggests that identical EE programmes may yield divergent behavioural outcomes across institutional contexts, underscoring that normative and regulatory frameworks influence the effectiveness of capability-building approaches. Thus, integrating insights from institutional theory and HCT provides a conceptual lens to understand how both the individual and structural frameworks determine EE's effectiveness.

2.2 Entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial outcomes

Entrepreneurship education is recognised for fostering innovation, employability, and economic resilience, though its impact varies across outcomes (Nabi et al., 2017; Secundo et al., 2020). Human capital theory links educational investment to productivity (Becker, 1964; Maritz et al., 2020), while institutional theory emphasises the role of regulatory and normative structures in shaping EE outcomes (Burns, 2017; Lamine et al., 2021). Together, these frameworks suggest EE should influence entrepreneurial mindset, intention, and action.

Empirical evidence (Nabi et al., 2017; Wong & Chan, 2022) converges on EE enhancing EM and EI, but diverges regarding EA, which is greatly context dependent. Programme design strongly mediates outcomes: experiential, feedback-rich formats outperform content-heavy approaches, and voluntary participation drives higher engagement than compulsory modules (Gielnik et al., 2015; Ripollés & Blesa, 2023).

Entrepreneurial mindset is consistently strengthened through self-efficacy, opportunity recognition, and creativity (Nabi et al., 2017; Cui & Bell, 2022), while EI, operationalised via theory of planned behaviour constructs, predicts EA but sensitive to both learners and institutional factors (Ajzen, 1991; Nowiński et al., 2019; Chang et al., 2022). EA, including prototyping and venture formation, is the least predictable outcome, requiring supportive design and enabling

environments (Shirokova et al., 2016; Piperopoulos & Dimov, 2019). Comparative analyses highlight that EE is not monolithic: learner responsiveness, delivery fidelity, and regulatory scaffolding determine the translation of mindset and intention gains into action (Kozlinska et al., 2020; Sorokin & Chernenko, 2022).

2.3 Conceptualising curriculum fidelity and its dimensions

Curriculum fidelity refers to the extent to which an educational programme’s content is delivered as designed, protecting key elements that underpin its theoretical basis (O’Donnell, 2008; Delaney et al., 2019). In EE, fidelity is especially crucial because experiential pedagogies require consistency to translate it into EM, EI, and EA. (de Leeuw et al., 2020; Tolmatcheff et al., 2024). According to scholars, a consensus converges on six core dimensions: content, adherence, exposure, quality of delivery, participant responsiveness, and assessment (McLeod et al., 2019; Ginsburg et al., 2024). Content fidelity ensures prescribed entrepreneurial competencies are covered, while adherence protects programme integrity against excessive instructor discretion (Combs et al., 2022). Exposure is secured through adequate intensity and duration, often safeguarded by credit-hour policies (Sánchez et al., 2021). The quality of delivery is dependent on trainers’ pedagogical skills and has a primary influence on outcomes (Combs et al., 2022), while participant responsiveness links classroom climate to student engagement (Ginsburg et al., 2024). Finally, fidelity assessment, using validated tools such as institutionalised accountability and structured rubrics, provides regulators with credible evidence of effective implementation (Powers et al., 2022; Nunes et al., 2024). Overall, conceptualising fidelity as a multidimensional construct strikes a balance between design and adaptation, making it central to both regulatory practice and scholarly evaluation in EE (Albers et al., 2024; Walton, 2024).

Table 1. Fidelity dimension, definition, and regulatory influence

Dimension of Fidelity	Definition in EE	Regulatory Influence	Key References
Content	Coverage of prescribed entrepreneurial competencies (e.g., opportunity recognition).	Accreditation bodies codify core learning outcomes frameworks, protecting content integrity from dilution.	Combs et al. (2022); Albers et al. (2024)

Adherence	Faithfulness to prescribed sequence, materials, and pedagogical methods	Mandated syllabi, audits, and QA mechanisms reduce instructor discretion, ensuring alignment.	Lemire et al. (2022); Hall & Dawes (2019)
Exposure (Dose)	Intensity and duration of practice opportunities (e.g., interviews, iterations, prototyping).	Credit-hour rules, contact-time minima, and timetable protections safeguard adequate exposure.	Sánchez et al. (2021); McLoughlin et al. (2021)
Quality of Delivery	Instructor competence, facilitation, and feedback quality.	Accreditation and staff-development policies enforce training, evaluation, and teaching standards.	Combs et al. (2022); McLoughlin et al. (2021)
Participant Responsiveness	Degree of student engagement and enactment of EE tasks.	Regulatory expectations for workload, participation, and assessment criteria support active engagement.	Ginsburg et al. (2024); Combs et al. (2022)
Assessment (Fidelity Measurement)	Systematic evaluation of whether EE was delivered/enacted as intended.	Assurance-of-learning frameworks require evidence via validated tools (e.g., OFES-CI, fidelity checklists).	Powers et al. (2022); Nunes et al. (2024)

2.4 Curriculum fidelity in higher education

Curriculum fidelity, originating in implementation science, captures how closely programmes are enacted as designed and is widely recognised as the mechanism aligning educational intent with learner outcomes (Stains & Vickrey, 2017; Delaney et al., 2019). Evidence from K–12 and health education shows consistent convergence: fidelity clarifies causal logic, reduces Type III errors, and identifies when strong delivery quality can compensate for incomplete adherence (de Leeuw et al., 2020; Capin et al., 2022; Tolmatcheff et al., 2024; Eiraldi et al., 2024). These insights become more consequential in EE programs and higher education, where deviation from curriculum intentions is common, converting evidence-based EE designs into passive formats that weaken the development of entrepreneurial competency (McLeod et al., 2019; Stains & Vickrey, 2017; Secundo et al., 2020).

Within EE, scholars converge on the view that fidelity is central to translating ambitious curriculum designs, such as venture labs or ecosystem engagement, into improvements in

entrepreneurial mindset, intention, and action. Divergent findings emerge, however, regarding whether strict adherence or structured adaptability best preserves outcomes, though studies (Harms, 2015; McLeod et al., 2019; Rosienkiewicz et al., 2024; Goli & Babu, 2024) consistently show that delivery inconsistency explains much of the variance in EE results. Therefore, fidelity assessment functions both as a methodological safeguard and a practical enhancement tool, ensuring that null or weak outcomes reflect theoretical, not implementation, limits. Recent work emphasises embedding fidelity monitoring through structured observations, enactment ratings, and aligned assessments to protect core pedagogical mechanisms while supporting informed adaptation (Hill, 2019; Walton, 2024; Albers et al., 2024; Ginsburg et al., 2024). This strengthens programme legitimacy and aligns EE more closely with regulatory, accreditation, and assurance-of-learning expectations.

H₁: Higher curriculum fidelity has a significant and positive impact on entrepreneurship education outcomes, including mindset, intention, and action.

2.5 Regulatory framework and entrepreneurial outcomes

Regulatory frameworks in higher education shape both the design and delivery of EE, extending beyond a simple direct influence on outcomes. From an institutional theory perspective, accreditation standards, quality assurance systems, and national policies define the “rules of the game” that guide programme implementation and evaluation (Urbano et al., 2019; Lamine et al., 2021).

First, regulatory frameworks can directly influence EEOs by signalling priorities, embedding employability and innovation targets, and aligning institutional practices with measurable outcomes. Evidence suggests that supportive policy environments enhance programme quality and performance, contributing to improvements in entrepreneurial mindset, intention, and action, although such effects remain contingent on effective implementation (Walter & Block, 2016; Huang et al., 2021).

Second, regulatory frameworks shape curriculum fidelity by prescribing standards for content, delivery, and assessment. Accreditation and assurance-of-learning mechanisms reduce variability in programme delivery and promote alignment with intended curricula, thereby strengthening implementation consistency (Mantai & Calma, 2022; Acevedo-De-los-Ríos & Rondinel-Oviedo, 2022).

Third, regulatory frameworks act as a contextual moderator of the fidelity–outcomes relationship. While regulation safeguards quality, excessive rigidity can constrain pedagogical flexibility, particularly in experiential learning contexts (Harvey, 2024; Romanowski & Karkouti, 2024). Consistent with the “firm, yet flexible” perspective, overly prescriptive frameworks may weaken the marginal benefits of high-fidelity delivery by limiting adaptive teaching practices (Albers et al., 2024).

Overall, regulatory frameworks operate as a multifaceted construct, serving as (i) an independent predictor of EEOs, (ii) an antecedent of curriculum fidelity, and (iii) a moderator of the fidelity–EEOs relationship. Although regulation influences fidelity, this study does not conceptualise curriculum fidelity as a mediator; rather, it adopts a direct and moderation framework to explain how regulatory conditions interact with implementation processes to shape EE outcomes.

H₂: *The regulatory framework has a significant and positive impact on curriculum fidelity.*

H₃: *The regulatory framework has a significant and positive impact on entrepreneurship education outcomes.*

H₄: *The regulatory framework positively moderates curriculum fidelity's impact on entrepreneurship education outcomes.*

Figure 1. Conceptual framework (Source: Authors' construct)

Figure 1 above presents a simple conceptual framework for the study. It illustrates that curriculum fidelity directly contributes to EEOs (EM, EI, and EA), reflecting the HCT mechanism, whereby when EE is implemented with high fidelity, students develop the expected outcomes. The regulatory framework serves as the contextual layer that shapes curriculum fidelity and ensures effective outcomes. This means that it moderates the fidelity-outcomes link, potentially amplifying it when regulation is outcome-focused and flexible, or dampening it when it is overly procedural, entrenching the institutional theory paradigm where rules and incentives establish the parameters under which high-fidelity teaching will produce entrepreneurial results.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted a quantitative, correlational research design, which is suitable for identifying associations between latent constructs without variable manipulation (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). Structural equation modelling (SEM) using SmartPLS 4.0 was employed to simultaneously assess direct and moderating relationships involving reflective constructs, allowing for a robust exploration of complex interaction effects (Hair et al., 2021).

3.2 Population and Sample

The study population comprises EE lecturers in selected Nigerian public universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education. These participants were purposively selected due to their central role in curriculum implementation and their exposure to regulatory and policy frameworks, positioning them as well-informed respondents for examining how policy shapes both programme delivery and outcomes (Davwet et al., 2019; Auta et al., 2023).

Although EEOs are conceptualised at the student level, lecturers are uniquely positioned to assess these outcomes through their direct involvement in curriculum delivery, assessment, and supervision of experiential learning activities. They routinely observe students' development of entrepreneurial mindset, intention, and action within structured learning environments. Consistent with prior research, instructors are often used as key informants in studies of curriculum implementation and learning outcomes, particularly where longitudinal student data are limited (Walter & Block, 2016; Nabi et al., 2017).

3.3 Sampling Technique

A purposive (heterogeneous) sampling method was adopted to select lecturers from the three categories of HEIs from South-West Nigeria, housing an intense cluster of public and private HEIs in the country, to ensure rigour, transparency, diversity, and capture diverse delivery (Memon et al., 2025). Additionally, they possess the experience and knowledge relevant to the research objectives, which enables the gain of contextual validity and depth in the findings (Ahmad & Wilkins, 2025). To minimise common method bias, procedural remedies such as anonymity and structured questionnaire design were applied, alongside statistical checks (VIF), which indicated no significant bias.

3.4 Data collection instrument

A structured questionnaire comprising multi-item scales was developed based on established and previously validated instruments. Curriculum fidelity dimensions were measured using adaptations from Hill and Erickson (2019), Teymurova et al. (2020), and Combs et al. (2022), while regulatory framework items were adapted from Boldureanu et al. (2020), Malebana and Mahlaole (2023), and Romanowski and Karkouti (2024). Entrepreneurship education outcomes were operationalised in terms of entrepreneurial mindset (EM), entrepreneurial intention (EI), and entrepreneurial action (EA), drawing on the works of Singh and Prasad (2016), Eze et al. (2016), Roundy et al. (2018), and Liu et al. (2021).

All items were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = “strongly disagree” to 5 = “strongly agree,” a format widely used in behavioural and educational research for its reliability and ease of interpretation. The questionnaire was organised into three sections: (i) curriculum fidelity dimensions, (ii) regulatory framework, and (iii) entrepreneurship education outcomes. While items were adapted to reflect the Nigerian higher education context, the original scale structures were retained to preserve construct validity.

To ensure clarity, relevance, and contextual appropriateness, the instrument was subjected to expert review and a pilot test involving a small group of lecturers before full-scale data collection. Feedback from the pretest resulted in minor wording refinements to enhance clarity and reduce ambiguity. The final questionnaire was administered via Google Forms, yielding 304 valid responses (93.8%), which is considered excellent for survey-based research (Booker et al., 2021). This exceeded the minimum required sample size of 324 determined using Yamane’s (1967) formula for finite populations.

3.5 Data analysis procedure

Data were analysed using SmartPLS 4.0, as it is suitable for reflective constructs and complex models involving moderating effects (Henseler et al., 2016; Hair et al., 2021). A two-step approach was employed, assessing the measurement model followed by the structural model. The measurement model was evaluated for reliability and validity using Cronbach’s alpha (CA), composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE), while discriminant validity was assessed using the Heterotrait–Monotrait (HTMT) ratio and the Fornell–Larcker criterion.

The structural model was then analysed to test direct and moderating relationships. Interaction terms were generated using SmartPLS’ moderation function (Chin et al., 2003), and bootstrapping with 5,000 resamples was used to assess path significance. Model fit was evaluated using the Standardised Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), with values below 0.08 indicating acceptable fit (Henseler et al., 2016). Given the use of self-reported data from a single source, common method bias (CMB) was addressed through procedural remedies, including respondent anonymity and separation of measurement sections. Harman’s single-factor test indicated no dominant factor, and variance inflation factor (VIF) values were below 5, suggesting that CMB is unlikely to be a serious concern (Hair et al., 2019).

Table 2. Respondents’ demographic profile

Institution type	FREQ	PERCT	Academic qualification	FREQ	PERCT
University	128	42%	HND	16	5%
Polytechnic	118	39%	BSc	38	13%
Colleges of Education	58	19%	MSc	132	43%
Total	304	100%	PhD	118	39%
			Total	304	100%
			Gender		
Academic position			Male	178	59%
Technologist	18	6%	Female	126	41%
Assistant Lecturer	32	11%	Total	304	100%
Lecturer III	16	5%			
Lecturer II	30	10%			

Lecturer I	42	14%	Teaching experience		
Senior Lecturer	48	16%	1 – 3	46	15%
Principal Lecturer	36	12%	4 – 6	60	20%
Assistant Professor	10	3%	7 – 9	36	12%
Associate Professor	22	7%	10 – 12	58	19%
Chief Lecturer	28	9%	13 – 15	38	13%
Professor	22	7%	above 15	66	22%
Total	304	100%	Total	304	100%
Age			Professional association		
25 – 29	26	9%	None	24	8%
30 – 34	22	7%	Member	118	39%
35 – 39	22	7%	Associate	64	21%
40 – 44	28	9%	Affiliate	22	7%
45 – 49	58	19%	Fellow	76	25%
50 – 54	62	20%	Total	304	100%
55 – 59	44	14%			
60 – 70	42	14%			
Total	304	100%			

Note: **FREQ** = frequency and **PERCT** = Percentage

3.6 Demographic report of respondents

This study provides a comprehensive overview of entrepreneurship education (EE) across South-West Nigerian higher education institutions, including universities (42%), polytechnics (39%), and colleges of education (19%), recognising that institutional differences influence curriculum fidelity (Ogundele et al., 2022). The respondents' strong academic background, with 82% holding postgraduate qualifications (43% MSc, 39% PhD), suggests that EE educators possess the theoretical grounding necessary for effective curriculum delivery (Adepoju & Akinola, 2021). Their academic positions, ranging from Technologist to Professor, ensure a diverse mix of experience and institutional roles, supporting the view that both junior and senior staff contribute meaningfully to entrepreneurship education (Onuoha & Worlu, 2020). Notably, over half of the

respondents have more than a decade of teaching experience, reinforcing the importance of experience in understanding policy frameworks and sustaining curriculum fidelity (Ojeifo, 2020).

The sample also reflects a relatively balanced gender composition (59% male, 41% female), supporting inclusive curriculum delivery in a field recognised as gender-sensitive (Uzuegbunam et al., 2021). The age profile, with a predominance of mid to senior-career academics, suggests a depth of experience aligned with evidence that such educators are better positioned to assess curriculum fidelity and policy dynamics (Phipps et al., 2025), consistent with patterns observed in Nigerian HEIs (Gabadeen & Raimi, 2012; Adetayo & Ogundele, 2020). Furthermore, the high level of professional affiliation among respondents indicates strong engagement with external networks and entrepreneurship ecosystems, which supports effective EE delivery and ongoing professional development (Oni & Gbadamosi, 2017; Ismail & Hassan, 2023).

Table 3. Indicator reliability, internal consistency, and convergent validity

Constructs	Item	Outer loadings	CA	CR	AVE
Entrepreneurial Action	EA1	0.810			
	EA2	0.603			
	EA3	0.791			
	EA4	0.664			
	EA5	0.667			
Entrepreneurial Intention	EI1	0.786			
	EI2	0.607			
	EI3	0.774			
	EI4	0.587	0.944	0.947	0.517
	EI5	0.780			
Entrepreneurial Mindset	EM1	0.633			
	EM2	0.665			
	EM3	0.744			
	EM4	0.683			
	EM5	0.792			
	EM6	0.827			
	EM7	0.727			
	EM8	0.725			
Fidelity of Implementation	FID1	0.796	0.891	0.892	0.699
	FID2	0.856			

	FID3	0.785			
	FID4	0.877			
	FID5	0.861			
Regulatory framework	RGF1	0.837			
	RGF2	0.886			
	RGF3	0.804	0.902	0.908	0.718
	RGF4	0.855			
	RGF5	0.852			

Table 4. Discriminant validity

Heterotrait-monotrait rasion (HTMT)				Furnell-Larcker criterion			
	EEO	FID	RGF		EEOs	FID	RGF
FID	0.784			EEOs	0.719		
RGF	0.628	0.700		FID	0.728	0.836	
RGF x FID	0.604	0.700	0.472	RGF	0.590	0.634	0.847

Table 5. Effect size of exogenous variables on endogenous variables

	R-square	F-Squared	
EEO	0.576	FID → EEOs	0.227
FID	0.402	RGF → EEOs	0.059
		RGF → FID	0.671
		RGF x FID → EEOs	0.043

Table 6. Variables collinearity test (VIF)

EA1	3.175	EI1	3.298	EM1	2.129	FID1	2.073	RGF1	2.649
EA2	2.224	EI2	2.093	EM2	2.493	FID2	2.593	RGF2	2.980
EA3	2.813	EI3	2.929	EM3	2.447	FID3	1.841	RGF3	2.214
EA4	2.535	EI4	2.304	EM4	2.799	FID4	3.477	RGF4	2.882
EA5	2.190	EI5	2.632	EM5	3.424	FID5	3.140	RGF5	2.780
				EM6	4.260				
				EM7	2.890				
				EM8	2.821				

Table 7. Structural Model (Hypothesis testing)

Structural model				
	Beta	STDEV	T statistics	P values

FID -> EEOs	0.478	0.051	9.424	0.000
RGF -> EEOs	0.205	0.049	4.225	0.000
RGF -> FID	0.634	0.039	16.381	0.000
RGF x FID -> EEOs	-0.109	0.030	3.675	0.000

Figure 2. Structural model (Source: SmartPLS output)

4. Data Analysis and Discussion

4.1 Measurement Model Assessment

The measurement model met conventional reliability and validity criteria. Most outer loadings satisfied or approached the ≥ 0.70 guideline, with several indicators in the 0.74 – 0.88 range, alongside a small number between 0.58 and 0.67. Retaining a limited number of sub-0.70 items is acceptable when composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) are adequate, and items preserve content validity (Hair et al., 2019). Construct reliability and convergent validity were satisfactory: the EEOs higher-order construct reported CA = 0.944, CR = 0.947, and AVE = 0.517; FID reported CA = 0.891, CR = 0.892, and AVE = 0.699; and RGF construct reported CA = 0.902, CR = 0.908, and AVE = 0.718. Discriminant validity was supported using the heterotrait–monotrait ratio (HTMT), with EEOs–FID = 0.784, EEOs–RGF = 0.628, and FID–RGF = 0.700, all below the conservative 0.85 threshold preferred for variance-based SEM (Henseler et al., 2015).

The Fornell–Larcker matrix showed square roots of AVE on the diagonal (EEOs = 0.719; FID = 0.836; RGF = 0.847); although the EEOs–FID correlation (0.728) slightly exceeded $\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$ for EEOs (0.719), the HTMT evidence and overall construct diagnostics justify discriminant validity. Collinearity was not problematic, with indicator VIFs ranging from 1.84 to 4.26, which is well below the conservative cutoff of 5 (Hair et al., 2019).

4.2 Structural model results

The structural model demonstrated moderate to substantial explanatory power, with R^2 values of 0.576 for EEOs and 0.402 for FID, which is appropriate for a prediction-oriented PLS-SEM application (Hair et al., 2019). The direct path from curriculum fidelity to EEOs was positive and statistically significant ($\beta = 0.478$, $t = 9.424$, $p < 0.001$), with a medium effect size ($f^2 = 0.227$). This is consistent with implementation-fidelity research, which shows that adherence to fidelity elements is associated with stronger learning and behavioural outcomes (de Leeuw et al., 2020; Stains & Vickrey, 2017). The path from RGF to FID was strongly positive ($\beta = 0.634$, $t = 16.381$, $p < 0.001$) with a large effect size ($f^2 = 0.671$), aligning with higher-education quality-assurance literature that links fidelity elements to more stable delivery and evidence systems (Mantai & Calma, 2022; Acevedo-De-los-Ríos & Rondinel-Oviedo, 2022). The direct path from RGF to EEOs was smaller but significant ($\beta = 0.205$, $t = 4.225$, $p < 0.001$; $f^2 = 0.059$), which aligns with the institutional perspective that accreditation and policy enable delivery mechanisms rather than directly driving students' learning outcomes (Walter & Block, 2016).

4.3 Moderation analysis results

The interaction between FID and RGF and on EEOs was significant but negative ($\beta = -0.109$, $t = 3.675$, $p < 0.001$; $f^2 = 0.043$), indicating that as regulatory stringency increases, the incremental impact of additional fidelity on EEOs weakens. The pattern is compatible with the “firm, yet flexible” view in implementation science, which recommends that standards protect core components while preserving adaptive space for experiential learning; excessive regulation can erode high-impact pedagogical activities and diminish returns to improved fidelity (Mantai & Calma, 2022; Albers et al., 2024; Romanowski & Karkouti, 2024).

Table 8. Hypothesis tests and decisions

Hyp	Structural path	β	t-value	p-value	Effect size (f^2)	Decision
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H1	FID → EEOs	0.478	9.424	0.000	0.227 (medium)	Supported
H2	RGF → FID	0.634	16.381	0.000	0.671 (large)	Supported
H3	RGF → EEOs	0.205	4.225	0.000	0.059 (small)	Supported
H4	RGF × FID → EEOs	-0.109	3.675	0.000	0.043 (small)	Supported (negative moderation)

EEOs = entrepreneurship education outcomes; FID = curriculum fidelity; RGF = regulatory frameworks. Decisions are based on f^2 benchmarks and bootstrapped significance as recommended for PLS-SEM reporting (Hair et al., 2019).

5. Interpretation of findings

This study examines how curriculum fidelity and regulatory frameworks jointly shape EEOs in higher education institutions in South-West Nigeria by linking what is delivered (curriculum fidelity) to what students achieve (EEOs) under regulatory conditions. The findings reveal a consistent pattern that integrates insights from HCT and institutional theory, highlighting both implementation quality and contextual conditions as critical drivers of outcomes.

5.1 H1: Does curriculum fidelity impact EEOs, including mindset, intention, and action?

Curriculum fidelity shows a strong and positive relationship with EEOs, indicating that programmes are most effective when delivered as designed. From the human capital theory perspective, this indicates that capability development depends not only on curriculum content but also on the consistency and quality of its implementation. Prior research highlights that experiential and feedback-rich pedagogies are critical for developing entrepreneurial mindset, intention, and action (Nabi et al., 2017; Wong & Chan, 2022), with evidence from action-based learning showing that student engagement with real-world tasks enhances entrepreneurial action (Gielnik et al., 2015). Thus, maintaining fidelity ensures that these core learning mechanisms are effectively translated into outcomes, underscoring the need to prioritise quality of delivery and authentic assessment rather than mere curriculum coverage (Ginsburg et al., 2024; Mantai & Calma, 2022).

5.2 H2: Does the regulatory framework shape fidelity?

The regulatory framework exhibits a strong positive influence on curriculum fidelity, indicating that formal structures play a key role in shaping programme delivery. From an institutional theory

perspective, incentives, rules, and quality assurance mechanisms establish the conditions under which entrepreneurship education is implemented, helping to reduce variability and align delivery with intended curricula (Mantai & Calma, 2022; Acevedo-De-los-Ríos & Rondinel-Oviedo, 2022). In practice, accreditation and assurance-of-learning processes act as stabilising mechanisms that limit delivery drift and make outcomes more verifiable. This is particularly evident in Nigeria, where compulsory EE has led to greater formalisation of syllabi and assessment practices despite institutional differences in resources (Oyinlola et al., 2024). Overall, the findings indicate that regulatory frameworks strengthen outcomes indirectly by improving the consistency and integrity of curriculum implementation.

5.3 H3: Does the regulatory framework impact EEOs?

The regulatory framework shows a positive but relatively modest influence on entrepreneurship education outcomes (EEOs), suggesting that policy contributes more by shaping enabling conditions than by directly driving student behaviour. From an Institutional Theory perspective, this influence operates through signalling priorities, embedding experiential expectations, and supporting industry linkages (Walter & Block, 2016). Consistent with prior evidence, institutional environments condition outcomes but do not substitute for effective pedagogy and student engagement (Nabi et al., 2017; Wong & Chan, 2022). This implies that regulatory standards are most effective when complemented by ecosystem supports, such as incubators, mentorship, and funding, which help translate entrepreneurial capabilities into action (Urbano et al., 2019; Oyinlola et al., 2024).

5.4 H4: Does the RGF moderate the FID impact on EEOs?

The regulatory framework negatively moderates the relationship between curriculum fidelity and EEOs, indicating that as regulatory stringency increases, the benefits of high-fidelity implementation weaken. From an institutional theory perspective, while regulation provides essential structure and guidance (Urbano et al., 2019; Lamine et al., 2021), excessive rigidity may constrain the flexibility required for experiential learning. This finding aligns with the “firm, yet flexible” principle in implementation science, which cautions that overly prescriptive systems can limit adaptive teaching practices and reduce the effectiveness of high-impact learning activities (Albers et al., 2024; Harvey, 2024; Romanowski & Karkouti, 2024). Thus, rather than

contradicting theory, the result refines it by highlighting regulation as a boundary condition that shapes how effectively curriculum fidelity translates into outcomes.

6. Discussion

This study explains variation in EEOs by linking curriculum fidelity with regulatory frameworks. Consistent with human capital theory, the findings show that outcomes improve when programmes are delivered as designed, reinforcing the importance of preserving experiential and feedback-rich pedagogies (Nabi et al., 2017; de Leeuw et al., 2020).

Regulatory frameworks also play a key role by shaping curriculum delivery. In line with Institutional Theory, accreditation and quality assurance systems provide structure and reduce variability, thereby strengthening fidelity (Mantai & Calma, 2022; Acevedo-De-los-Ríos & Rondinel-Oviedo, 2022). However, their direct influence on outcomes appears limited, suggesting that policy primarily enables effectiveness through implementation rather than directly driving student behaviour (Walter & Block, 2016; Wong & Chan, 2022). Importantly, regulatory frameworks also condition how fidelity translates into outcomes. The negative moderation effect indicates that increasing regulatory rigidity weakens the benefits of high-fidelity implementation. This supports the “firm, yet flexible” argument that overly prescriptive systems can constrain adaptive, experiential teaching practices (Albers et al., 2024; Harvey, 2024; Romanowski & Karkouti, 2024).

Overall, the findings highlight that the effectiveness of curriculum fidelity depends on the regulatory context. While regulation enhances quality, excessive rigidity may limit pedagogical innovation, positioning regulatory frameworks as both enabling and constraining forces in entrepreneurship education.

6.1 Theoretical implications

By integrating HCT with institutional theory, the study enriches EE theory by linking how EE works to the contexts in which it is effective. Modelling fidelity as a multidimensional construct and EEOs as a pathway from EM to EI to EA clarifies the design–implement–outcome architecture, often implied but rarely estimated in combination. The large regulation-to-fidelity path validates the institutional framework, the medium fidelity-to-EEOs path validates human-capital mechanisms, and the negative moderation adds a boundary condition that tempers broad assumptions about regulation’s strengthening role.

6.2 Practical implications

Curriculum designers should specify core components and guardrails while crafting fidelity checklists tied to their elements for authentic assessment over proxy tests. For institutions/QA units, instrument fidelity dashboards should be incorporated within assurance-of-learning cycles, while quality reviews should be on student outcomes, rather than relying solely on documentation. Educators should prioritise coaching-intensive and feedback-rich practices that raise engagement and action knowledge. Policymakers/accreditors should set outcome-centric standards with proportionate regulations and leave pedagogical discretion to adapt to the context of institutions, as they operate under varying resource conditions; ultimately, capabilities can be converted into action for national interest.

7. Conclusion, limitations, and future research directions

7.1 Conclusion

This study examined how curriculum fidelity and regulatory frameworks shape entrepreneurship education outcomes (EEOs) in higher education institutions in South-West Nigeria. The findings show that while fidelity improves outcomes, regulatory frameworks enhance implementation but may weaken its impact when overly rigid. The study contributes in three ways. Theoretically, it integrates Human Capital Theory and Institutional Theory to show that outcomes depend on both capability development and institutional conditions. Methodologically, it models both direct and moderating effects using PLS-SEM. Contextually, it provides evidence from Nigeria, highlighting how regulation interacts with implementation in practice. Overall, the findings suggest that regulatory systems should ensure quality while allowing flexibility for experiential learning.

7.2 Limitations and future research directions

With cross-sectional designs relying solely on instructor reports, future work should employ longitudinal and multilevel designs that track the mindset-intention-action chain and probe the nonlinear effects of regulation to identify its optimal point. A comparative study across the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria and other SSA systems can help clarify how to balance consistency with high-impact and adaptive pedagogy.

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